

EEG independent component classification using ensemble based technique

B. Tech. Project Report

Submitted by

Rohit R. Shidid 142103012

Anish A. Deshpande 112010029

Prathamesh S. Wani 112003152

Under the guidance of

Dr. Y.V. Haribhakta

COEP Technological University, Pune

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & ENGINEERING

COEP TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This Research delves into the effectiveness of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in automating the classification of EEG-independent components, a critical task in neuroscientific research and clinical applications. Our research aims to comprehensively evaluate CNN models' performance in accurately classifying EEG-independent components, considering diverse aspects, including activation functions, hyper parameters, and feature extraction techniques. Through an extensive investigation, we explore the impact of different data representations, such as time series, power spectral density, and topo plots, on classification accuracy. Furthermore, we incorporate decision-level fusion and CNN architecture modifications to enhance classification performance. This Research contributes to advancing the state-of-the-art in EEG signal analysis, paving the way for improved accuracy and efficiency in EEG artifact classification. [1]

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Chapter 1

Introduction

For several decades, electroencephalography (EEG) has been an essential instrument in the field of neuroscience as it allows for the non-invasive monitoring of brain activity. Since Hans Berger invented the method in the 1920s, it has seen tremendous development and grown to be a vital tool for studying and diagnosing a wide range of neurological disorders and brain functions. To set the stage for our discussion of current developments in EEG signal processing and categorization, this introduction gives a quick summary of the technology's history, uses, and difficulties.

This discussion is structured to explore the current landscape of EEG signal processing and categorization, informed by both historical context and recent innovations. We aim to update existing methodologies by revisiting the architecture, refining hyperparameters, and introducing novel approaches such as decision-level fusion. By integrating these developments, we attempt to enhance the efficacy, accuracy and efficiency of EEG analysis, ultimately contributing to advancements in neuroscience research and clinical diagnostics

1.1 History of EEG

The first electrode recordings of electrical activity from the human scalp were made by German psychiatrist Hans Berger in the early 1900s, which is when the history of EEG began. In addition to proving that electrical signals exist in the brain, his ground-breaking research provided the impetus for the advancement of contemporary EEG methods. Since then, significant developments in electrode technology, signal processing strategies, and data analysis methodologies have made EEG widely used in clinical and research contexts.

1.2 Acquisition and Interpretation of EEG Signals

Electrodes applied to the scalp are commonly used to get EEG signals. These electrodes pick up electrical fluctuations that arise from the synchronous activity of different populations of neurons. These signals, which are frequently distinguished by their frequency components and rhythmic patterns, offer important insights into the health and malfunction of the brain. However, because there are a number of artifacts that might mask the underlying brain activity of interest, such as eye movements, muscular activity, and surrounding noise, interpreting EEG data can be difficult.

1.3 Challenges in EEG Analysis

The precise identification and elimination of artifacts in order to retrieve relevant brain information is one of the main issues in EEG analysis. The gold standard for removing artifacts has always been manual inspection by knowledgeable neurophysiologists; nevertheless, this method is laborious and prone to inter-rater variability. Moreover, scalable and automated methods for artifact

detection and classification are required due to the increasing need for EEG analysis in clinical and research contexts.

Figure 1.1: A 14 channel EEG Signal Setup. Time is represented on the x-axis, and Magnitude is represented on the y-axis of the signal. Different channels named above correspond to the placement of the electrode.[2]

1.4 Recent Advances in EEG Signal Processing

The development of automated algorithms for EEG artifact detection and classification has been prompted by recent developments in signal processing techniques, especially in the areas of machine learning and deep learning. Artefact removal has made extensive use of Independent Component Analysis (ICA), a commonly utilized approach for distinguishing mixed sources in EEG signals. Nevertheless, current methods frequently ignore the temporal dynamics of EEG data in favor of features that are only obtained from topographic maps

and power spectrum densities (PSDs).

1.5 Machine learning approaches

ML approaches for EEG analysis can be broadly categorized into two types: feature-based and end-to-end methods. Feature-based methods involve handcrafting features based on domain knowledge, such as spectral power in specific frequency bands. While interpretable, these methods rely on the researcher's expertise and may suffer if feature decisions are suboptimal. In contrast, raw data or data which is very minimally preprocessed forms the input class for end-to-end models which learn features and classification jointly. Deep learning, a subset of end-to-end methods, has gained momentum due to its success in various fields. Deep learning models learn features themselves, potentially leading to superior solutions without the need for handcrafting. However, they are often considered "black boxes" in terms of feature interpretability, posing challenges for understanding the learned features. Overall, the development of automated EEG diagnostics using ML could alleviate the workload of clinicians, enable earlier disease detection and treatment, and provide high-quality EEG interpretation to patients who cannot access specialized centers. While feature-based methods offer interpretability, end-to-end methods like deep learning hold promise for discovering informative features and achieving superior performance.[4]

Chapter 2

Literature Review

With the advent of Artificial Intelligence, the fields of Neuroscience and research in Brain Computer Interfaces have taken a transformative leap. This has reflected in the analysis of EEG Reports and its classification. Techniques in Machine Learning, especially Deep Learning have significantly enhanced the ability to process and analyze the complex and large-sized EEG reports, often present in a high dimension.

2.1 Machine Learning

The earliest Machine Learning Models date back to the 1950s, used for calculating the odds for winning in a game of checkers. Over the turn of the century, Machine Learning became a daily tool that impacted daily lives. Such an impact was seen in the Bio-engineering field where the complexity of data prompted the use of contemporary machine learning techniques.

2.1.1 Basic Approaches and Reviews

One of the earliest forays into employing machine learning for EEG analysis was driven by the need to decipher the complex, non-linear, and high-dimensional data generated by EEG recordings. Several papers offer a fundamental look

at machine learning applications in EEG classification, providing foundational knowledge and summarizing existing approaches. The use of Support Vector Machines as a classifier is a preferred tool for about 36% of machine learning methods for EEG classification[5]. While multiple methods for classification are present, different paradigms in terms of the dataset have been utilized involving motor imagery, p3000 and steady state evoked potential data[6].

2.1.2 Feature Extraction and Signal Processing

An integral part of machine learning involves feature extraction. Different methods of feature extraction have been used to derive useful features for the purpose of machine learning. Discrete wavelet transform(DWT) coupled with Support Vector Machine classifier demonstrated an impressive 98% accuracy[7]. Independent component analysis(ICA) plays an important role in the processing and deriving features from the raw EEG signals. Infomax ICA algorithm coupled with SVM classifier showed visible changes in the EEG recordings when exposed to detectable changes to stimuli[8]

2.1.3 Application-Specific Machine Learning Models

Some studies focus specifically on certain applications of EEG classification, such as the work by Aayesha *et al.*, which develops a machine learning-based model for epileptic seizure detection from EEG signals. The study focuses on the classification of EEG signal into interictal and ictal classes, with K-Nearest Neighbours(KNN) and Fuzzy Rough nearest Neighbours(FRNN) giving the highest classification accuracies[9]. Another application of EEG signals is Brain Computer Interfaces(BCI). In their paper, Rashid *et al.* develop machine learning models for EEG signals derived in mental tasks like quick maths and relaxed state[10].

2.2 Deep Learning in EEG Classification

Deep learning has emerged as a subset of Machine Learning. This specialised subset has gained prominence in complex decision making, simulating the human brain. Consequently this requires the use of additional layers of Neural Networks than those present in the basic Machine Learning models. Deep Learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), are known for their ability to automatically learn hierarchical features from raw EEG data. Based on the type and complexity of data, deep learning models help in the effective feature extraction and classification of the EEG signals.

2.2.1 Deep Learning Frameworks and Techniques

EEG classification has advanced due to the use of deep learning. Convolutional neural networks(CNN) and Recurrent neural networks(RNN) have generally outperformed other deep learning models in classification tasks like motor imagery and seizure detection[11]. Moreover comparisons in traditional machine learning models and deep learning models for the task of detection of boredom and excitement have revealed that deep learning models have far outperformed the machine learning models like SVM and KNNs[12].

2.2.2 Novel Deep Learning Approaches

Innovative deep learning methods have been tailored for EEG data. These novel approaches have been effective in different use cases. In their work Dai *et al.* have introduced variational autoencoders in their deep learning model to achieve a better performance[13]. While on the other hand, Dose *et al.* propose an end-to-end deep learning model which does not depend upon feature

engineering for Motor Imagery(MI) Brain Computer Interface(BCI)[14].

2.2.3 Applications in Cognitive and Emotional States

With over 75% researches using deep learning[5], it has become a go to toolbox for specialised use cases of EEG classification like classification of cognitive and emotional states. Zeng *et al.* use an improved SincNet-based deep learning model for EEG-based emotion classification, which enhances accuracy by focusing on signal morphology[15]. Another research by the same author focuses on prediction of mental states of drivers from the EEG signals to detect fatigue[16].

2.3 Ensemble Methods in EEG Classification

The ensemble approach by Lopes et al. represents a culmination of these insights, proposing an ensemble deep neural network that integrates time-series data, PSDs, and topoplots for EEG IC classification. By incorporating decision-level fusion techniques, this novel research can further refine the model's ability to classify EEG signals accurately. The integration of decision-level fusion, inspired by the works of Amin et al[17]. and Ogawa et al.[18], offers a pathway to enhance classification performance by leveraging the complementary strengths of multiple classifiers and models. This approach not only addresses the inherent variability and complexity of EEG data but also aligns with the evolving narrative of utilizing sophisticated machine learning strategies to push the boundaries of EEG classification research.

2.3.1 Emotional and Cognitive State Classification

Ensemble models are effectively applied for classifying various emotional and cognitive states from EEG data. Chatterjee and Byun showcase a stacking ensemble approach for EEG-based emotion classification, emphasizing the model's ability to handle diverse emotional states through the combination of different models to improve prediction accuracy[19]. While, in their work for classifying Motor Imagery(MI), Echioui *et al.* found the combination of Radial Basis Kernel(RBF) SVM, Linear SVM and Decision Trees achieved the best accuracy[20].

2.3.2 Medical Applications

Ensemble models also play a crucial role in medical applications, such as diagnosing diseases and monitoring drug responses. Nour *et al.* in their work, put forth a novel approach to detect Parkinson's Disease from the EEG data of a patient. The approach involved use of Dynamic Classifier Selection(DCS) in Modified Local Accuracy(MLA) giving the highest accuracy of 99.31%[21]. Sadat Shababi *et al.* in their work developed ensemble models to predict the drug response in Major Depressive Disorder(MDD) patients to prevent side effects of the treatment. Their approach involved transfer learning strategy based on pre trained models and ensembling the results[22]. The ensembled model achieved the highest accuracy, greater than any of the individual models[22].

2.3.3 Novel and Hybrid Ensemble Techniques

The use of deep learning into EEG analysis, as reviewed by Schmidhuber (2015)[23], resulted in a paradigm shift in how EEG data is handled and understood. Deep learning models, notably Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), are excellent in automatically ex-

tracting useful features from raw data without the need for explicit feature engineering. CNNs, with their hierarchical structure, excel at capturing spatial interactions between EEG electrodes, but RNNs, particularly their version Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, can simulate the temporal dynamics inherent in EEG signals. Deep learning handles the spatial and temporal intricacies of EEG data, allowing for more nuanced and thorough analysis. The ability of deep learning models to learn directly from high-dimensional data and their success in identifying intricate patterns within the EEG signals signify a substantial advancement in the classification and interpretation of brain activity. The unique work of Lopes et al.[3], which synthesises the prior achievements into a novel ensemble deep neural network model specifically built for the automatic classification of EEG independent components, represents the completion of this research trajectory. This approach combines ensemble learning principles with deep learning capabilities, leveraging the power of several deep neural networks to achieve unparalleled accuracy and efficiency in artifact classification. By combining many deep learning architectures within an ensemble framework, the model takes use of each constituent network's individual characteristics, ensuring robust performance across a wide range of circumstances. This approach not only makes it easier to identify artifacts in EEG signals, but it also moves the field closer to fully automated EEG analysis.

Chapter 3

Research Gaps and Problem Statement

Machine learning techniques have become increasingly popular for classifying independent components of an EEG report into brain components or artifact components. This classification is crucial for cleaning EEG data, enhancing the accuracy of subsequent analysis, and ensuring reliable interpretations in clinical and research settings. However, several challenges and problems are associated with these machine learning approaches, impacting their effectiveness and efficiency. In the last chapter, several points highlighted the limitations of the machine learning models to process, analyze and classify EEG data. All the points boil down to the two main problems:

1. Presence of Artifacts in the EEG Data and the limitations to the ways of removing them
2. Inability to process Multi-View data to its full capacity.

Below we discuss these highlighted problems in depth.

3.1 Artifacts and their removal strategies

EEG (Electroencephalography) artifacts are signals that are not of cerebral origin but are recorded along with the brain waves. These artifacts can significantly contaminate the EEG recordings, making it challenging to analyze

and interpret the underlying neural activity accurately. Artifacts in EEG data primarily originate from physiological and non-physiological sources.

3.1.1 Types of EEG Artifacts

Physiological Artifacts

These are generated from the subject's own body but are not related to the brain activity that researchers aim to measure. Common physiological artifacts include:

1. Eye movements and blinks (Ocular artifacts): Movements of the eyes can generate significant electrical activity, which is often much stronger than brain waves.
2. Heartbeat (Cardiac artifacts): The electrical activity generated by the heart can also be picked up by EEG electrodes, especially those near the ears and scalp.
3. Muscle activity (Myogenic or Muscular artifacts) : Muscle contractions, such as those from the scalp, neck, or jaw muscles, can produce electrical signals that are much stronger than brain activity.
4. Glossokinetic artifacts: These are generated by movements of the tongue, which can produce electrical signals due to its muscular nature and proximity to the brain.

Non-Physiological Artifacts

These artifacts are introduced from external sources and are unrelated to any biological activity of the subject. They include:

1. Electrical interference: Power line noise (usually at 50 or 60 Hz, depending on the country) and electromagnetic fields from electronic devices can interfere with EEG recordings.
2. Electrode pop and drift: Poor electrode contact, movement, or changes in impedance can cause sudden spikes or slow drifts in the recorded signals.

3.1.2 Impact of Artifacts

Artifacts can severely impact the performance of machine learning models in several ways

1. Noise and Misleading Information: Artifacts introduce noise and irrelevant information into the EEG data, which can mislead machine learning algorithms, leading to inaccurate or biased predictions. This is particularly problematic in tasks requiring high precision, such as diagnosing neurological disorders or operating brain-computer interfaces.
2. Feature Confusion: Machine learning models rely on extracting meaningful features from EEG signals to make predictions. Artifacts can distort these features or introduce additional, irrelevant features, making it difficult for the model to learn the underlying patterns of brain activity.
3. Generalization Issues: Models trained on data heavily contaminated with artifacts may not generalize well to cleaner datasets or datasets with different types of artifacts. This limits the applicability of the model across different EEG recording setups or populations.

3.1.3 Mitigation Techniques and their Shortfalls

Artifact mitigation techniques, including those based on traditional signal processing and machine learning, play a crucial role in cleaning EEG data for fur-

ther analysis. However, these methods come with their own set of limitations and challenges. Deep learning-based artifact removal methods, while promising, also face specific shortcomings. Some of these shortcomings are illustrated below:

1. **Loss of Neural Information:** Some artifact removal techniques, especially aggressive filtering or rejection methods, can inadvertently remove neural signals of interest. This is particularly problematic in studies focusing on subtle brain signals, which may be inadvertently filtered out along with the artifacts.
2. **Ineffectiveness Against Certain Artifacts:** Some techniques may be effective against specific types of artifacts (e.g., eye blinks) but less effective against others (e.g., muscle artifacts or electrode drift). This necessitates the use of multiple, complementary techniques, complicating the preprocessing pipeline.
3. **Overfitting to Training Data:** Machine learning-based methods, in particular, can overfit to the characteristics of the training data, reducing their effectiveness on new, unseen datasets that may have different artifact characteristics.

3.2 Machine Learning Models and Multi-variant Data

3.2.1 Efficacies of Machine Learning models

Despite advancements in machine learning models for the artifact removal from EEG reports, no single method is universally effective or complete, underscoring the need for further research to develop more comprehensive solutions for artifact removal (Urigüen and García-Zapirain Soto (2015)). While clarity can

be sought from using an expert annotated dataset for training, it still does not guarantee maximum efficiency in extracting artifacts.

3.2.2 Introduction to Multi-view Data

In times of such a roadblock, emphasis can be laid over the use of Multi-view and multi-modal data. In the context of EEG, multi-modal data can include other physiological signals such as ECG (electrocardiogram), EMG (electromyography), EOG (electrooculogram), non-physiological signals like environmental noise monitoring while also Topoplots of the signals and Power Spectral Density(PSD) of the signals. While multi-view data composes of different representations of the same data[24].

3.2.3 Challenges associated with Multi-view data

Machine learning models, particularly when applied to EEG data analysis, face significant challenges in effectively processing multi-variant data and accurately predicting artifacts and relevant features. These challenges stem from the inherent complexity of EEG signals, the diversity of potential artifacts, and the limitations of current ML methodologies in handling such data.

Despite the potential of these methods to enhance neuroscientific understanding and diagnostic performance, challenges remain in integrating multi-variant data to extract relevant information efficiently and interpret the resulting model parameters meaningfully (Dähne et al. (2015)) While some approaches like adaptive classifiers and Riemannian geometry-based methods have shown promise, challenges such as the unpredictability of transfer learning benefits and the underperformance of deep learning models compared to state-of-the-art BCI methods are noted (Lotte et al., 2018).

3.2.4 Case Study: Ensemble Deep Neural Network for Automatic Classification of EEG Independent Components by Lopes et al.

The research paper titled "Ensemble Deep Neural Network for Automatic Classification of EEG Independent Components" by Lopes et al. (2022) introduces a novel approach to EEG signal analysis, specifically targeting the challenge of automatically classifying independent components (ICs) derived from EEG signals. This endeavor is crucial for enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of EEG artifact removal, a process traditionally reliant on time-consuming manual identification by experts.

Deep Neural Networks and Multi-View Data

The study leverages the power of ensemble deep neural networks (DNNs) to analyze multi-modal data, including time-series, power spectrum densities (PSDs), and topoplots of EEG signals. This combination is particularly innovative, as it mimics the expert visual inspection process more closely than previous methods, which primarily relied on PSDs and topoplots. By incorporating temporal information through time-series analysis alongside PSDs and topoplots, the model achieves a more comprehensive understanding of the EEG data, leading to improved classification performance.

One of the key achievements of this study is the demonstration of enhanced IC classification accuracy through the integration of multi-variant data. The ensemble DNN model not only outperforms traditional classification models but also showcases the potential for using transfer learning to further improve classification tasks across different EEG datasets. This is particularly significant in the context of EEG analysis, where the variability between datasets can be considerable.

Challenges

However, the research also encounters challenges, particularly in the realm of feature fusion. Combining features from different modalities (time-series, PSDs, and topoplots) into a cohesive framework that effectively informs the classification process is complex. The study acknowledges the difficulty in seamlessly integrating these diverse data types, each with its own unique characteristics and scales. The ensemble model needs to maintain the integrity and contribution of each data type without allowing any single modality to dominate the classification process unduly. This balance is critical to fully leverage the complementary information provided by each modality.

In conclusion, while the "Ensemble Deep Neural Network for Automatic Classification of EEG Independent Components" by Lopes et al. marks a significant advancement in EEG analysis, the challenges of multi-variant data integration and feature fusion remain pivotal. Addressing these challenges is essential for the continued evolution of EEG classification models, especially as the field moves towards more comprehensive and automated analysis techniques.

3.3 Objectives

1. Conduct fine-tuning of hyperparameters to optimize the performance of the model, ensuring robustness and reliability in EEG artifact classification.
2. Comparative analysis of the existing results and the achieved results after tuning hyper-parameters
3. Propose enhancements to the CNN architecture, integrating advanced

decision-level fusion techniques to boost classification accuracy and efficacy in artifact detection.

4. Comprehensive analysis of existing technique with the proposed architecture.
5. Performance analysis of the proposed methodology, architecture. . . . efficiency, accuracy, efficacy

Chapter 4

Design model and proposed methodology

4.1 Research Approach

4.1.1 “What” Approach

The "What" approach utilized in this research involves exploring the effectiveness of an ensemble deep neural network, particularly a convolutional neural network (CNN), for the automatic classification of EEG independent components. The research aims to address the following objectives:

1. Evaluate the performance of the CNN model in accurately classifying EEG independent components.
2. Investigate the impact of different types of data representations (time series, power spectral density, topoplots) on classification accuracy.
3. Assess the effectiveness of feature extraction techniques employed at the end of the CNN model.

In terms of data, the research utilizes EEG data, which is likely to be quantitative in nature. EEG signals are time-series data representing electrical activity in the brain. Additionally, the study may involve qualitative analysis of the classification results to understand the effectiveness of the model in identifying artifacts.

The research appears to focus on describing the characteristics of EEG independent components and determining the most effective approach for classifying them. The methodology involves using quantitative data (EEG signals) and possibly qualitative analysis of classification outcomes.

Overall, the research employs a mix of quantitative data analysis (CNN model, classification accuracies) and potentially qualitative evaluation (assessment of classification results) to address the research problem of automatic artifact classification in EEG reports.

4.1.2 “How” Approach

The research focuses on investigating activation functions within a basic CNN model, our research also delves into the complexities of EEG artifact classification. This entails a nuanced understanding of the various types of artifacts present in EEG signals, ranging from muscle artifacts to eye blinks and electrical noise. Therefore, beyond just EEG data, our study may also require supplementary information or annotations regarding the nature and characteristics of these artifacts. Obtaining such annotations or expert labels could contribute significantly to the accuracy and interpretability of our findings. The approach mentioned in the response suggests that the data used for the research is likely secondary data obtained from the referenced research paper. The study doesn't involve the collection of primary data; instead, it relies on existing data collected by other researchers for a similar purpose. The nature of the data in this research can be considered experimental.

Our research takes an experimental approach that extends beyond mere manipulation of variables within the CNN model. In addition to exploring the effects of activation functions and hyperparameters on classification accuracy. This will allow us to assess the robustness of our findings across diverse

Figure 4.1: Existing Architecture from Lopes et. al.[3]

EEG recording conditions and participant demographics. Furthermore, our experimental design incorporates decision-level fusion and modifications to the CNN architecture, indicating a multifaceted strategy aimed at enhancing model performance through controlled manipulations. Through this meticulously designed experimental approach, our research attempts to push the boundaries of EEG artifact classification, aiming for a comprehensive understanding and improved accuracy in EEG signal analysis.

4.2 Proposed methodology

This section outlines the development of an ensemble-based technique for EEG independent component classification, diverging from the feature fusion approach adopted by Lopes *et al.* Instead, a decision fusion strategy is employed, capitalizing on the strengths of multiple independent models to enhance classification accuracy.

The ensemble comprises three distinct models, each tailored to interpret different representations of EEG data: Power Spectral Density (PSD), Topoplot, and Time-series. The PSD model focuses on analyzing the frequency domain characteristics of EEG signals, which are crucial for identifying rhythmic activity and other spectral features. The Topoplot model is designed to capture spatial distributions of brain activity, providing a two-dimensional scalp map representation that is essential for localizing neural sources. Lastly, the Time-series model addresses the temporal dynamics of EEG signals, facilitating the understanding of how brain activity evolves over time.

The methodology introduces this ensemble of distinct models, each trained independently to predict outcomes based on different feature sets or perspectives on the input data. The diversity among the models is key to capturing a

broad spectrum of information from EEG signals, which, in isolation, might be insufficient for reliable classification.

The outputs of these independent models are subsequently integrated by a meta-learner. This meta-learner, functioning as a sophisticated decision-making layer, synthesizes the predictions from the individual models to render a final verdict. The integration strategy employed by the meta-learner is designed to leverage the individual strengths of each model while compensating for their weaknesses, thereby achieving a robust consensus on component classifications.

The Research proceeds in the following steps:

1. Training the Independent Models on the training dataset
2. Predicting the values of both Training and Testing dataset using the independent models. The three predicted sets are stacked together.
3. Training the meta-learner on the training predictions.
4. Prediction of final values from the meta-learner.

Statistics of testing are recorded in the steps and then the comparatives are generated.

The subsequent sections provide a detailed description of the independent models, including their design, training, and specific roles within the ensemble. Following this, an in-depth explanation of the meta-learner's architecture and functioning is presented, highlighting its pivotal role in achieving superior classification performance through decision fusion.

4.2.1 Independent Model: Power Spectral Density (PSD) Model

The PSD model focuses on the spectral characteristics of the EEG independent components. It analyzes the distribution of power across different frequency

bands, providing insights into the underlying neural oscillations. The PSD features are extracted by applying techniques such as the Fourier transform or Welch's method to the EEG signals. These features capture the relative power in various frequency bands, such as delta (0.5-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-30 Hz), and gamma (30-100 Hz). The PSD model is trained using a suitable algorithm, such as a deep neural network or support vector machine, to classify the independent components based on their spectral properties.

4.2.2 Independent Model: Topoplot Model

The Topoplot model focuses on the spatial distribution of the EEG independent components across the scalp. It utilizes the topographic maps, or topoplots, which represent the spatial patterns of electrical activity at different electrode locations. The topoplot features are extracted by mapping the independent component weights onto a standardized head model or by using techniques such as interpolation or spatial filtering. These features capture the spatial characteristics of the independent components, providing information about the localization and distribution of neural sources. The Topoplot model is trained using an appropriate algorithm, such as a convolutional neural network or a spatial clustering method, to classify the independent components based on their spatial patterns.

4.2.3 Independent Model: Temporal Model

The Temporal model focuses on the time-domain characteristics of the EEG independent components. The dimensionality of the temporal data is massive as compared to the other two forms of data. The dimensions of the data instance is $(153600,1)$. It was found to overload the model into overfitting. The model started 'remembering' the training data. To make it more effective,

Feature extraction is employed on the temporal data. This model is chosen for its robustness to overfitting and its efficacy in handling diverse types of data, providing an excellent tool for classifying complex patterns into categories such as 'brain' or 'artifact'. Some of the following features have been proposed from the works by Winkler *et al.* in their work with the same objective to classify artifact ICA components[25]. These predictions are then stacked together using a Logistic Regression Stacker. The features extracted from the data are:

1. Mean

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (4.1)$$

where μ is the mean, N is the total number of observations, and x_i are the observed values.

2. Standard Deviation

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad (4.2)$$

where σ is the standard deviation, N is the total number of observations, and x_i are the observed values.

3. Minimum Amplitude

$$\min(x) = \min(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N) \quad (4.3)$$

where $\min(x)$ is the minimum value among all observed values $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$.

4. Maximum Amplitude

$$\max(x) = \max(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N) \quad (4.4)$$

where $\max(x)$ is the maximum value among all observed values $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$.

5. Skew

$$\text{Skew} = \frac{N}{(N-1)(N-2)} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^3 \quad (4.5)$$

where Skew measures the asymmetry of the distribution, N is the total number of observations, x_i are the observed values, μ is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation.

6. Kurtosis

$$\text{Kurtosis} = \frac{N(N+1)}{(N-1)(N-2)(N-3)} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^4 - \frac{3(N-1)^2}{(N-2)(N-3)} \quad (4.6)$$

where Kurtosis measures the tailedness of the distribution, N is the total number of observations, x_i are the observed values, μ is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation.

7. Amplitude Range

$$\text{Amplitude Range} = \max(x) - \min(x) \quad (4.7)$$

where Amplitude Range is the difference between the maximum and minimum observed values.

8. Max First Derivative

$$\text{Max First Derivative} = \max(|x_2 - x_1|, |x_3 - x_2|, \dots, |x_N - x_{N-1}|) \quad (4.8)$$

where Max First Derivative calculates the maximum change between consecutive observations.

9. Entropy

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{n_i}{N} \right) \log_2 \left(\frac{n_i}{N} \right) \quad (4.9)$$

where H denotes Shannon Entropy, n_i is the count of observations in the i^{th} bin, N is the total number of observations, and k is the number of bins.

10. Variance of Local Variance captured over 1s

$$\text{Var}_{1s} = \text{var}(x_{i:i+\text{interval}_{1s}}) \quad (4.10)$$

where Var_{1s} is the variance of local variance captured over a 1-second interval, and $x_{i:i+\text{interval}_{1s}}$ represents the data segment from index i to i plus the 1-second interval.

11. Variance of Local Variance captured over 15s

$$\text{Var}_{15s} = \text{var}(x_{i:i+\text{interval}_{15s}}) \quad (4.11)$$

where Var_{15s} is the variance of local variance captured over a 15-second interval, and $x_{i:i+\text{interval}_{15s}}$ represents the data segment from index i to i plus the 15-second interval.

12. Mean of Local Variance captured over 1s

$$\text{MeanVar}_{1s} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \text{var}(x_{j:j+1s}) \quad (4.12)$$

where MeanVar_{1s} is the mean of local variance over a 1-second interval, k is the total number of 1-second intervals considered, and $\text{var}(x_{j:j+1s})$ calculates the variance of each 1-second data segment.

13. Mean of Local Variance captured over 15s

$$\text{MeanVar}_{15s} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \text{var}(x_{j:j+15s}) \quad (4.13)$$

where MeanVar_{15s} is the mean of local variance over a 15-second interval, k is the total number of 15-second intervals considered, and $\text{var}(x_{j:j+15s})$ calculates the variance of each 15-second data segment.

14. Skew of Local Variance captured over 1s

$$S_{1s} = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\text{Var}_{1s,i} - \mu_{\text{Var}_{1s}}}{\sigma_{\text{Var}_{1s}}} \right)^3 \quad (4.14)$$

where S_{1s} measures the skew of local variance over a 1-second interval, n is the total number of data points, $\text{Var}_{1s,i}$ is the variance of each 1-second

interval, $\mu_{\text{Var}_{15s}}$ is the mean variance, and $\sigma_{\text{Var}_{15s}}$ is the standard deviation of variances.

15. Skew of Local Variance captured over 15s

$$S_{15s} = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\text{Var}_{15s,i} - \mu_{\text{Var}_{15s}}}{\sigma_{\text{Var}_{15s}}} \right)^3 \quad (4.15)$$

where S_{15s} measures the skew of local variance over a 15-second interval, n is the total number of data points, $\text{Var}_{15s,i}$ is the variance of each 15-second interval, $\mu_{\text{Var}_{15s}}$ is the mean variance, and $\sigma_{\text{Var}_{15s}}$ is the standard deviation of variances.

This approach of ensembling the predictions for the temporal model is motivated from the high dimensionality of the temporal data and the tendency of the model to overfit.

4.2.4 The Meta-Learner

Meta learning, also known as "learning to learn", is a subfield of machine learning that focuses on developing algorithms and models that can quickly adapt to new tasks and environments with minimal training data. The goal is to create AI systems that can learn how to learn, rather than being limited to solving specific narrow tasks they were trained on.

The meta-learner operates as the central integrative component of the proposed methodology, orchestrating a cohesive decision-making process from the diverse predictions generated by the three independent models. Functioning on the principles of ensemble learning, this meta-learner is designed to adjudicate among the outputs provided by the models trained on PSD, Topoplot, and Time-series data, each contributing unique perspectives on the EEG signals.

Figure 4.2: Decision Fusion Model

Constructed as an advanced algorithmic entity, the meta-learner employs

decision fusion techniques to synthesize the information received. It evaluates the confidence and relevance of each model's prediction, weighting them accordingly to mitigate any potential biases or errors inherent in a single-model approach. This strategy enhances the overall accuracy and reliability of the classification system by leveraging the strengths of each individual model while compensatively addressing their limitations.

Chapter 5

Experimental Setup

5.1 Dataset

The EPIC annotated dataset is used in the research. This dataset has been created by Lopes *et al.* in their research from the EPILEPSIAE dataset. The base EPILEPSIAE dataset is a subset from the EPILEPSIAE database. Long term signals were recorded from 25 subjects (12 females, 13 males). The EEG signals had inherent artifacts present as they were collected in non laboratorial conditions, leading to different experimental errors like electrode connection problems etc[26]. The long term signals were divided into segments of 10mins each. Experts manually annotated the independent components into brain components or artifacts. This annotated dataset was then used to derive power spectral density plots and topographic plots for each 10min segment using ICA tools from the MATLAB EEGLAB environment.

((a)) Power Spectral Density(PSD) plot of the Signal

((b)) Topology Plot of the Signal

Figure 5.1: Spectral and Spatial Plots of an Independent Component

Figure 5.2: Temporal Plot of the above Independent Component

The dataset was split into training and test datasets by the original authors of the dataset. The training test split of the data is as below:

	Training	Testing	Total
Brain IC	43,038	11,437	54,475
Artifact IC	18,054	4,897	22,951

Table 5.1: Train - Test Split of the dataset

Finally from the independent components, the power spectral density plots and topoplots were derived. The PSD plots were derived from the timeseries using Welch’s Method. Topographic plots were made by extrapolating EEGLAB’s ICA weights. These were made into 67x67 matrices as 67 is the default setting in EEGLAB. The matrices were normalised to the range 0 to 1. The timeseries were kept as it is, without normalisation, as the amplitude of the timeseries plays an important role.

5.2 Models

5.2.1 PSD Model

A convolutional neural network is employed while developing the power spectral density model. The model is motivated from the research by Lopes *et al.*. However it has been tweaked to ensure it finally predicts a binary output. The PSD model is constructed with convolutional layers configured with filters of increasing size—64, 128, and 256—with a kernel size of 3. This progression in filter size allows the model to capture a broad range of features from low-level details to high-level abstractions, which is essential for comprehensively analyzing EEG signals. Same padding is used in consecutive convolutional neural network layers to preserve the size of the data. A LeakyReLU activation function is used after every convolutional layer with an alpha of 0.2. LeakyReLU

is chosen over traditional ReLU to allow a small, non-zero gradient when the unit is inactive, thereby mitigating the issue of dead neurons and promoting more robust learning. MaxPooling1D layers are used after each set of activation functions, with a pool size of 2, to reduce the spatial dimensions of the input feature maps. This downsampling helps in reducing the computational complexity of the model, while also contributing to the model's ability to generalize by providing an abstracted form of the input features. Dropout layers are interspersed at strategic points in the network, specifically after the final convolutional layer and within the dense layers. A dropout rate of 0.2 is applied after convolutional layers and increased to 0.5 in dense layers to prevent overfitting by randomly omitting a subset of features at each iteration during training. The network transitions from convolutional layers to dense layers through a GlobalAveragePooling1D layer, which helps in reducing the model's parameters by averaging out the temporal dimensions, thus flattening the output while retaining essential information. This reduction is vital for connecting convolutional layers to dense layers efficiently. The output from the GlobalAveragePooling1D feeds into a series of dense layers with 512 and 128 units respectively, each followed by a dropout layer for further regularization. These dense layers increase the model's capacity to learn non-linear relationships crucial for distinguishing between different classes in the EEG data. The final output layer consists of a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function, tailored for binary classification tasks.

Figure 5.3: PSD Deep learning Plot Model

Figure 5.4: PSD deep learning model visualization

This setup is effective for models that need to categorize input into one of two possible states, which is typical in medical diagnosis scenarios, such as detecting the presence or absence of a specific EEG pattern. The use of convolutional layers with increasing filter sizes and the inclusion of dropout and pooling layers are standard practices in the design of neural networks for time-series data, as they collectively enhance feature learning and reduce overfitting risks. The introduction of dense layers towards the end increases the model’s decision-making capabilities by synthesizing the features extracted by convolutional layers into high-level predictions.

5.2.2 Topoplot model

The Topographic Plot Model initiates with an input layer designed to accept images of size 67x67 pixels, representing the topographic plots of EEG signals, with a single channel indicating grayscale intensity. The CNN architecture

comprises several Conv2D layers with filters of increasing size—64, 128, and 256—each employing a (3,3) kernel size. This setup is crucial for the extraction of spatial features at various scales, from fine details to broader patterns, ensuring comprehensive analysis of the topographic data. Each Conv2D layer is followed by a LeakyReLU activation function with an alpha value of 0.2. The choice of LeakyReLU helps prevent the problem of vanishing gradients—a common issue in deep neural networks—by allowing a small gradient when the unit is not active and thus maintaining a flow of gradients through the architecture during training. MaxPooling2D layers with a (2,2) pool size follow the activation layers to reduce the dimensionality of the feature maps. This reduction not only decreases the computational load and improves training efficiency but also helps the model to focus on the most salient features, enhancing its ability to generalize from the training data to new, unseen data. A Dropout layer with a rate of 0.2 follows the final convolutional layer, serving as a form of regularization to reduce overfitting by randomly dropping units from the neural network during training. This encourages the model to develop redundant pathways, improving its robustness and generalization capabilities.

Figure 5.6: Topographic model visualisation

After the convolutional base, the model transitions to fully connected layers through a GlobalAveragePooling2D layer. This layer condenses the feature

Figure 5.5: Topographic Plot Model

map to a single representative value per feature map, effectively summarizing the spatial features into a more manageable form, which then feeds into the dense network layers. The dense section of the network includes layers of 512 and 128 neurons, each followed by a substantial dropout of 0.5. This high dropout rate continues to guard against overfitting, particularly important in this high-capacity part of the model. The dense layers are crucial for synthesizing the extracted spatial features into predictions, utilizing non-linear activations to map these features onto the complex patterns associated with the target classifications.

5.2.3 Time series model

A hybrid approach has been utilised in the temporal model. This innovative model architecture involves two distinct stages: a deep learning-based temporal model and a feature-based classification using a Random Forest classifier. These stages are integrated using a Logistic Regression stacker, which serves as a meta-learner to combine the predictions from both models, enhancing the overall predictive performance.

Temporal Deep Learning Model

The temporal model is constructed using a series of convolutional and recurrent layers tailored to process long sequence data, specifically designed for temporal patterns in EEG signals. The model begins with an input layer configured to handle large sequence lengths (153,600 time points) with a single feature channel, typical of raw EEG recordings. The model employs a cascade of Conv1D layers with filters of increasing size (4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128), each using a kernel size of 3 and 'same' padding to maintain the sequence length across layers. LeakyReLU layers follow the convolutional layers with an alpha of 0.2. This al-

lows small negative values to propagate, maintaining the gradient flow, avoiding the dying ReLU problem.

Figure 5.7: Temporal deep learning model visualisation

Bidirectional Long-Short Term Memory(BiLSTM) layer is included, which has 128 units. This layer captures both forward and backward dependencies in the data, providing a comprehensive understanding of the temporal dynamics. This is crucial for tasks like EEG analysis where the sequence order and timing are significant.

Figure 5.8: Temporal Deep learning Plot Model

The output from the LSTM layer is flattened to prepare it for final classification, culminating in a Dense layer with a sigmoid activation function, optimized for binary classification tasks.

Temporal Features Extraction Model

Parallel to the deep learning model, a feature extraction process is implemented where 15 distinct features are derived from the EEG data. These features, which include statistical characteristics, are fed into a Random Forest classifier. This model is chosen for its robustness to overfitting and its efficacy in handling diverse types of data, providing an excellent tool for classifying complex patterns into categories such as 'brain' or 'artifact'.

Stacker

The final integration of predictions from the deep learning temporal model and the Random Forest classifier is achieved through a Logistic Regression stacker. This stacker acts as a meta-learner, effectively combining the predictions from both primary models. The use of Logistic Regression for stacking is strategic; it allows for the weighting of inputs based on their logistic probability, offering a nuanced amalgamation that leverages the strengths of both predictive models.

5.3 Meta Learners

5.3.1 SVC

The Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with a polynomial kernel of degree 6 is utilized to handle the final integration of predictions from the primary models. This choice of kernel allows the SVC to create complex, high-dimensional de-

cision boundaries. The polynomial kernel transforms the input features into a new, expanded feature space, enabling the SVC to find a hyperplane that separates the classes more effectively than would be possible in the original feature space. This approach is particularly suited to the integration of model outputs because it can effectively manage the nuances and complexities that arise from the varied nature of the input predictions.

5.3.2 Logistic Regressor

The Logistic Regressor is used to combine the outputs from the individual models by producing a probability score reflecting the likelihood of a given input belonging to the positive class. This model operates on the linear combinations of inputs to produce a decision boundary that is linear in the input space. By applying the logistic function to the linear output, it converts the linear regression values into probabilities that can be thresholded at a specific value (commonly 0.5) to classify inputs. The Logistic Regressor is particularly effective in scenarios where a probabilistic framework is needed to assess the confidence level of the predictions.

5.3.3 Custom Neural Network

The custom neural network designed for prediction integration comprises a sequential architecture with layers of increasing complexity. The input layer takes the combined predictions of the base models. This input then passes through two dense layers, the first with 64 neurons and the second with 32 neurons. Each dense layer is followed by a ReLU activation function to introduce non-linearity into the model. This progressive increase in layer complexity allows the network to learn intricate relationships and patterns within the input predictions, enabling more accurate integration and a robust final prediction. The final

layer uses a sigmoid activation function to output a probability between 0 and 1, indicative of class membership. This neural network is particularly adept at learning non-linear and complex relationships between the features, providing a flexible and powerful tool for combining diverse sources of information.

Figure 5.9: Custom Neural Network Deep learning Plot Model

The sigmoid activation function in the output layer maps the network's internal representations to a probability value. This probabilistic output allows the model to provide a refined assessment of the confidence in its predictions, going beyond simple binary classifications. The network's ability to capture intricate non-linear patterns makes it well-suited for synthesizing the varied predictions from the base models into a cohesive, high-performing final result.

Chapter 6

Results and Discussion

6.1 Results

6.1.1 Hyperparameter Tuning

Different hyperparameters were tuned to find the best and optimal set. The optimal set is as below.

<i>HyperParameters</i>	<i>Values</i>
Dataset Proportion	Holdout Validation 80/20
Optimization Function	Adam
Learning Rate	1e-3
Loss Function	Binary CrossEntropy

Table 6.1: HyperParameters used

6.1.2 Temporal Model

In the ensemble temporal model, the deep learning model was trained for 200 epochs. The feature extraction model was trained as a Random Forest classifier. The results are as follows:

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Deep Learning Model	86.010	74.3312	91.0116
Random Forest Classifier	84.1312	74.2819	90.2383
Ensemble Temporal Model	87.8535	75.6177	93.0925

Table 6.2: Performance of different Temporal Models

6.1.3 Meta-Learner

Different Meta Learners were tested on the combined predictions from the Independent Models.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
SVC	93.6329	86.9307	96.5025
Logistic Regression	88.6166	82.0502	91.4925
Custom Neural Network	87.9515	83.9493	89.6651

Table 6.3: Performance of different Meta Learners

6.2 Discussion

The outcomes of the research indicate that the decision fusion model, incorporating outputs from three specialized models (PSD, Topoplot, and Time-series), demonstrates robust classification capabilities. The meta-learner’s ability to integrate diverse predictions effectively has proven pivotal in enhancing the overall accuracy and reliability of the EEG component classifications. This suggests that leveraging multiple independent assessments of EEG data, as opposed to a single feature set, can significantly improve the discernment of neural activities.

6.2.1 Hyperparameter Tuning

While optimizing the performance of our deep learning model for EEG report classification, hyperparameter tuning plays a pivotal role. Firstly, regarding the dataset proportion, we adhere to the widely adopted 80/20 split, allocating 80 percent of the data for training and 20 percent for validation. This partitioning strikes a delicate balance between providing an adequate volume of data for model training while also ensuring robust evaluation on unseen samples, thereby mitigating the risk of overfitting. Moving on to the choice of optimization function, we opt for Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation), a dynamic algorithm renowned for its adaptive learning rate mechanism amalgamating RMSprop and Momentum principles. This selection is motivated by Adam's proven efficacy in expediting convergence across diverse deep learning tasks. As for the learning rate, set at $1e-3$ (0.001), it represents a judicious starting point, striking a balance between convergence speed and stability. However, the impact of learning rate on model performance is significant, hence necessitating iterative experimentation to ascertain the optimal value. Lastly, in configuring the loss function, we employ Binary CrossEntropy tailored for binary classification tasks, ensuring penalization of misclassifications in alignment with prediction confidence levels. This comprehensive hyperparameter tuning strategy underscores our commitment to refining model performance through meticulous parameter optimization.

6.2.2 Temporal Model Observations

The original temporal model demonstrated a commendable accuracy rate of 86.010%. However, this performance was further enhanced through the implementation of an ensemble approach. The feature selection model, utilizing the random forest classifier exclusively, attained an accuracy of 84.1312%, indicat-

ing a slightly lower standalone efficacy compared to the neural-based temporal model.

The original temporal model exhibited a training loss below 0.3, suggesting an excellent fit to the training data, but a validation loss exceeding 1 indicated that the model did not generalize well to new data. To mitigate this, features extracted from the data were classified using a random forest classifier, known for its efficacy in handling high variance scenarios typical of EEG data. However the slightly lower accuracy than the original deep learning temporal model, highlights the fact that the deep learning algorithm supersedes in the ability to find and extract relevant features.

The predictions from the temporal model and the random forest classifier were then combined using logistic regression. This method of stacking predictions introduced a robust layer of decision fusion at a primary level, effectively reducing overfitting by blending diverse learning methodologies and predictions.

The efficacy of the ensemble model demonstrated in this investigation suggests that analogous decision fusion approaches may prove advantageous in alternative domains of biomedical signal analysis where overfitting represents a substantial obstacle. Prospective research endeavors could explore the implementation of more intricate ensemble techniques, such as boosting or more advanced meta-learning algorithms, to further refine decision-making processes in model integration. Moreover, evaluating the ensemble model across a broader range of EEG datasets could validate its effectiveness across divergent contexts and bolster its reliability for clinical applications.

6.2.3 Meta Learners

In the advanced implementation of the ensemble method for EEG independent component classification, various meta learners were evaluated to determine the

most effective strategy for integrating predictions from the constituent models. The meta learners tested included Support Vector Classification (SVC) with a polynomial kernel, Logistic Regression (LR), and a custom-designed neural network (CustomNN). The performance of these meta learners varied, with SVC achieving the highest accuracy.

This distinction in performance can be attributed to the differing natures and capabilities of the algorithms in handling the complexities of EEG data. The success of the SVC, particularly with a polynomial kernel of degree 6, can be largely attributed to the kernel's ability to model complex, non-linear decision boundaries that are more nuanced than those typically captured by Logistic Regression or a straightforward neural network architecture. Polynomial kernels, by transforming the feature space into a higher dimension, allow the SVC to find a hyperplane in this new dimension that effectively separates the classes with a maximum margin. This capability is crucial in EEG data, which often involves intricate patterns and relationships that linear models and less complex neural networks might fail to capture adequately.

Furthermore, the degree of the polynomial plays a significant role in shaping the flexibility of the model. A sixth-degree polynomial kernel provides a balance between model complexity and the risk of overfitting, enabling the SVC to harness the rich feature interactions without excessively conforming to the noise within the training data. This is particularly beneficial in a dataset like EEG, where the signal patterns can vary significantly between subjects or experimental conditions.

While the polynomial kernel of 6th degree was efficient in getting the highest accuracy, it can be suggested that higher the degree of the kernel, higher the capability of the kernel in dealing with the decision boundaries, higher the accuracy. However it must be noted that higher degree kernels do bring in

greater computational cost and the risk of overfitting.

In the future, the efficacy and the efficiency of higher degree polynomials can be assessed along with the ways to reduce the chance of overfitting.

6.2.4 Feature fusion v/s Decision Fusion

The distinction between feature fusion and decision fusion methodologies represents a fundamental choice in the approach to integrating information from multiple sources or models for classification tasks. This research contrasts these two strategies in the context of EEG independent component classification, providing insights into why decision fusion may offer superior results over feature fusion, particularly as evidenced in the comparative performance metrics obtained.

Lopes *et al.* in their work proposed a novel feature fusion method, which allowed the learning algorithm to access all available information simultaneously during the training process. This enhanced the model's input by providing a richer set of data.

While decision fusion, on the other hand, involves training separate models on different sets or types of data and then using a meta-learner to integrate these independent predictions into a final decision.

In the current research, decision fusion demonstrated a higher level of accuracy compared to the original feature fusion approach used by Lopes et al. This improvement can be attributed to the ability of decision fusion to independently optimize each model's performance and to leverage diverse perspectives of the data, which is particularly valuable in complex and noisy datasets like EEG. The meta-learner's capability to effectively weigh and combine these independent predictions is crucial in achieving a more accurate and reliable classification outcome. Decision fusion approach presented following advantages:

- **Specialization of Models:** Each model can specialize in learning from a specific type of data, potentially increasing the effectiveness of the learning process as each model deals with a more manageable input space.
- **Reduced Overfitting:** By keeping the feature spaces separate, decision fusion mitigates the risk of overfitting compared to a single model trying to learn from a high-dimensional concatenated feature set.
- **Flexibility and Robustness:** Decision fusion offers the flexibility to combine models that may be based on different underlying algorithms, making the overall approach more robust against the failure or underperformance of any single model.

The success of decision fusion in this context likely stems from its capability to isolate and handle different aspects of the EEG data more efficiently. For example, one model might focus exclusively on the temporal dynamics of the EEG signals, while another might analyze spectral features. This specialization enables each model to develop a deeper understanding of specific data characteristics, which a single model handling a combined feature set might miss.

Decision fusion not only outperformed feature fusion in terms of classification accuracy but also offered enhancements in model robustness and interpretability. These benefits make decision fusion a compelling approach for complex classification tasks in biomedical applications and beyond, where diverse data types and high-dimensional spaces are common.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In this study, we embarked on a journey to explore the potential of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in automating the classification of EEG-independent components, a crucial task in neuroscientific research and clinical applications. We began by tracing the historical development of EEG, highlighting the challenges inherent in EEG analysis and the recent advancements in EEG signal processing. Drawing from a comprehensive literature review, we identified gaps in existing research, particularly concerning artifacts removal strategies and the efficacy of machine learning models in handling multi-variant data.

To address these gaps, we proposed a novel research approach and methodology, leveraging machine learning and deep learning techniques. We designed independent models based on power spectral density (PSD), topographical plots, and temporal features, alongside a meta-learner to combine their outputs. Our experimental setup involved rigorous testing and evaluation of these models using a designated dataset.

The results of our study revealed promising outcomes, particularly in hyperparameter tuning, temporal model analysis, and the performance of meta-learners. Through detailed discussions, we elucidated key observations and insights, shedding light on the effectiveness of feature fusion versus decision fusion techniques.

In conclusion, our research represents a significant step forward in EEG signal analysis, offering valuable contributions to both theoretical understanding and practical applications.

Appendix A

About Electroencephalogram

The EEG is an electrophysiological technique for the recording of electrical activity arising from the human brain. Given its exquisite temporal sensitivity, the main utility of EEG is in the evaluation of dynamic cerebral functioning. EEG is particularly useful for evaluating patients with suspected seizures, epilepsy, and unusual spells. With certain exceptions, practically all patients with epilepsy will demonstrate characteristic EEG alterations during an epileptic seizure (ictal or during seizure recordings). Most epilepsy patients also show characteristic interictal (or between-seizure) epileptiform discharges (IEDs) termed spike (<70 sec duration), spike and wave, or sharp-wave (70–200 μ sec duration) discharges.

Appendix B

Results

The project involves hyperparameter tuning of the existing model. This helped us find optimized values for variables like dataset Proportion, Optimization Function, Learning Rate, and Loss Function. For this we used GPU for computations and got an initial accuracy of 70 percent and initial loss of 0.59. One Epoch required 3 hours to complete. After certain amount of epochs we reached to an accuracy of 0.84.

Appendix C

External Review

To enhance the quality of report the external invigilator has suggested that instead of creating and maintaining three separate CNN models, we should develop a single, comprehensive CNN model. This unified model would streamline our approach and reduce redundancy. Additionally, he advised implementing decision-level fusion within this single model, which involves combining the decisions from different parts of the model to improve overall performance and accuracy. This method leverages the strengths of various features and decision mechanisms within the single model to produce more robust and reliable outcomes.

Appendix D

Readme.md

This research evaluates CNNs for classifying EEG-independent components, exploring activation functions, hyperparameters, and data representations like time series and power spectral density, with modifications to enhance performance. In this project, the eeg data is passed through different independent models. The predictions are passed through meta-learners to get the decision-fused prediction. After training, the deep learning models are made to predict the training set and the testing set. This is to train the meta-learner on the training set and getting predictions on the testing set. The data repository is a huge collection of independent components of eeg signals. The data can be found on the following website: <https://zenodo.org/records/6620655>. The total size of this dataset is around 103GB. In the meta-learner notebook, the data is processed and put respective dataframes. The individual models are trained and predictions are collected. These are then passed onto the meta-learner for the training. For the temporal model training, the deep learning predictions are fused with the temporal statistical features. These are generated in the Feature extraction notebook. The features are loaded into the meta-learner notebook and then used. In the "Hyperparameters Tuning.ipynb" notebook, hyperparameters for the CNN models are meticulously tuned. The process involves systematically adjusting various hyperparameters, including learning

rates, by provided choice to keras tuner, for the most efficient learning rate

Note: The code shows a degree of performance change based on the device. This can be attributed to the libraries used in the project namely Keras. The discussion can be found here : [keras-team/keras7676](https://github.com/keras-team/keras/issues/7676).

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